

**PRECEDENT PHENOMENON AND ITS TYPES IN UZBEK LITERARY
TEXTS**

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Abstract: The aim of this article is to study the problem of precedent text and to classify the main types of precedent phenomena in Uzbek literary texts. One of the main purposes of the article is to demonstrate how a precedent text functions in literary texts using an example of an artistic example. In various illustrations from different sources, it is stated that literary texts, folklore genres give different types of precedent phenomena to express the perception of a social group. An attempt is made to show how a precedent phenomenon in a literary text can reflect the social worldview of people of different cultures in order to comprehend a certain situation.

Key words: precedent text, precedent name, precedent statement, precedent situation, intertextuality, typology, mythological characters, symbol.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi o'zbek badiiy matnlarida pretsedent matn muammosini o'rganish va pretsedent hodisalarining asosiy turlarini tasniflashdan iborat. Maqolaning asosiy maqsadlaridan biri badiiy namuna misolida badiiy matnlarda pretsedent matn qanday ishlashini namoyish etishdir. Turli manbalardan olingan turli xil namunalarda badiiy matnlar, folklor janrlari ijtimoiy guruh idrokini ifodalash uchun turli xil pretsedent hodisalarni berishi ta'kidlangan. Badiiy matndagi pretsedent hodisa muayyan vaziyatni tushunish uchun turli madaniyatdagi odamlarning ijtimoiy dunyoqarashini qanday aks ettirishi mumkinligini ko'rsatishga harakat qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: pretsedent matn, pretsedent nom, pretsedent bayonot, pretsedent vaziyat, intertekstuallik, tipologiya, mifologik qahramonlar, ramz.

Аннотация: Целью данной статьи является изучение проблемы прецедентного текста и классификация основных типов прецедентных явлений в узбекских художественных текстах. Одна из основных целей статьи - продемонстрировать, как прецедентный текст функционирует в художественных текстах, на примере художественного примера. На различных иллюстрациях из разных источников утверждается, что литературные тексты, фольклорные жанры дают различные типы прецедентных явлений для выражения восприятия социальной группы. Предпринята попытка показать, как прецедентное явление в художественном тексте может отражать социальное мировоззрение людей разных культур для осмысления определенной ситуации.

Ключевые слова: прецедентный текст, прецедентное имя, прецедентное высказывание, прецедентная ситуация, интертекстуальность, типология, мифологические персонажи, символ.

INTRODUCTION

The term precedent phenomena were coined by Russian linguists first time in order to study the words and phrases used in the study of one's own and foreign cultural heritage, such as films, plays, folklore, art and etc. When people speak they do not always pay attention to the origin of the words or phrases that they use but they have an idea where they come from. The expressions that they present can be represented by proper nouns and a set of phrases or they can be taken from famous books, movies or events of this culture. These specific language units are called precedent phenomena.

The precedent phenomena are understood as culturally loaded signs, known to a significant part of the representatives of the national-cultural community. Zolotarev defines precedent phenomena as "culturally specific language units, functioning in a text". The use of precedent texts is based, most often, on the transformation of the component composition of "old" known phrases and expressions, which undoubtedly enhances their expressive capabilities. This definition determines precedent phenomena according to modern tendencies in linguocultural studies as "discourse units that are regularly renewed in speech, known to all members of the national-

linguistic and cultural community, and have a common minimized connotatively colored perception invariant, the appeal to which is understandable without additional decoding”.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

During the last 25 years the concept of precedent phenomena has been developed significantly. As a result, “precedent phenomenon” now serves as an umbrella term for various loosely related notions such as literary allusion, cultural reference, idiom and proverb. Roughly speaking, the development of the concept of precedent phenomena has undergone three stages (Mikhail Zolotarev, 2013. p.4).

The Russian linguist Yuri Karaulov was the first person who used the term “precedent text” in 1980s. Karaulov defined it as a special text 1) which is meaningful for an individual because of its informative and emotive values; 2) which is well-known to a wide milieu surrounding the individual, including his predecessors and contemporaries; and 3) allusion to which is constant in the spoken discourse of the individual (Mikhail Zolotarev, 2013. p.4).

About at the end of 1990s three Russian scholar groups published their works on this topic. In 1997 some linguists such as Viktoria Krasnykh, Dmitry Gudkov, Irina Zakharenko and D. Bagaev presented their large scientific works.

They learnt the Karaulov's term detailed and decided that average members of an ethnic-cultural group should know this term well. According to them, precedent phenomena plays a great role to enhance the cognitive base of the nation. That kind of base of information is beneficial and valuable especially to language users because it defines their linguistic worldview. The first classification of the precedent phenomena was given by Krasnykh and they divided precedent phenomena into verbal and non-verbal types. As verbal types they define precedent texts, precedent situations, precedent names and precedent sayings. Also, they point out that there is a certain change in understanding behind every precedent event-a simplified sign known to most native speakers.

Precedent phenomena is an umbrella which embraces precedent name, precedent text, precedent statement and precedent situation. Precedent name is considered as an individual name which is connected with a widely known person. For example: Tumaris, Alisher Navai, Farhad, Shirin and etc.

In particular, Darvishov Ibrahim, who is considered one of our linguist scientists, defines precedent units in his manual as follows: "In linguistic culture, the main place is occupied by the study of important concepts of culture and precedent names. Precedent names are famous names associated with very famous texts (such as Qori Ishkamba, Maysara, O'tkuri), and related to situations (such as Jaloliddin, Mahmud Tarobiy, Shiroq). Some famous names belonging to the culture of the Uzbek people are also distinguished by the fact that they belong to the universal culture: Farobi, Khorezmi, Ibn Sina, Amir Temur, Navoi, Ulugbek, etc." [Darvishov, 2021, p.56]

Precedent names in Uzbek cultures are classified in three main categories:

1. Names of historical figures: Zahiriddin Bobur, Alpomish. Chulpon.
2. Names related to religion: Муҳаммад, Ойша, Yusuf, Fotima, Abubakir, Sulaymon.
3. Names taken from works (novels, plays and stories): Majnun, Layli, Farmonbibi, Otabek, Kumush.

Here is an example, from the president Mirziyoyev's speech at the Art school and museum named after Abdulla Kadiri in December, 2019 comprises the name of Abdulla Kadiri (Abdulla Qodiriy): A self-respecting person would read "Bygone Days" by Abdulla Kadiri not one, but several times. (Mirziyoyev's Speech at the Art school and museum named after Abdulla Kadiri, Dec. 27, 2019). Every Uzbek who heard this speech admires that Kadiri was not only a great writer, but also a great patriot with knowledge and potential. A name of a fictional character can turn into a precedent phenomenon too, for example Khoja Nasreddin Afandi.

A precedent situation is an ideal, standard situation with some connotations that are popular and known to members of the linguocultural community. A precedent situation, according to D. Gudkov, is "a real single situation, the minimized invariant

of perception of which includes the idea of the action itself, its participants, the main connotations and assessments. It is part of the cognitive base of the linguistic and cultural community and is familiar to almost all its socialized members. communities" (Gudkov, 2000, p. 41). The Combined Forces of Temur and Amir Husayn begin a campaign against the armies of Ilyaskhoja, who were expelled from Movarounnahr in 1365. This battle, which is between Tashkent and Chinoz, takes the name of the famous "mud battle" (Loy jangi) in history.

Moreover, precedent situation is represented in language and speech either by the name of a person/people or organization involved in some noted event or by a place name where it took place. No doubt, the place name Samarqand Darvoza (Samarkand Gate) has become a precedent phenomenon. Though it is the name of the complex of modern and entertaining in capital city, it is widely accepted as the name of one of the gates built in the city defense wall of Tashkent in the Middle Ages.

Precedent texts are "language units that are significant in cognitive or emotional relations for a certain person, of an abnormal character, that is, good for the circle to which this person belongs, including his predecessors and contemporaries, and lastly, repeated over and over again in the speech of this linguistic person" [Karaulov Yu, 2010, p.217]. The precedent texts include works of fiction (for example, "Shum bola", "Bolalik", Ikki eshik orasi"), texts of well-known songs (for instance, Uzbek national song "Dutorim").

Advertisements, jokes (To illustrate Askia-satirical word game between two or more than two people) Gulmisiz, rayxonmisiz yo sumbulmisiz? –Aytganizman. Men sizni o'xshatdim, etc. The essential forms of precedent text include the forms that are based on the linguistic mechanism of allusion, such as: phraseological units, proverbs, citations, aphorisms, children's poems, songs and media texts. For example, "Qo'rqqanga qo'sh ko'rinar", "O'z uying-o'lan to'shaging", "Zumrad va Qimmat", "Ur to'qmoq", etc. Very often precedent texts may be expressed by children's poems or the songs. This fact explains one of the major features of precedent texts its universality, recurrence (often usage) and ability to be easily coded and understood.

“Zumrad stayed alone. At that moment a strong wind began to blow. It bound the axe to the tree and shook it. It made a sound of cutting a tree. Zumrad waited for her father for a long time, it got dark, but he didn't come” or “Now go up to the attic. There are two boxes: one is red, and another is white. Go and take the red one.”

The writers often use such kind of precedent texts in order to visualize the appearance or characteristics of the hero: Zumrad was a very beautiful, kind and clever girl. Qimmat was a very lazy and arrogant girl at home. Kenja Botir's handsome body and strong arms made him look even stronger (O'zbek national fairy tales).

The reference to the precedent text can be repeatedly renewed in the process of communication through precedent statements, precedent situations or precedent names associated with this text. For example, the reference to the precedent text “O'tgan kunlar” (Begone days) precedent text can be carried out through the names-Otabek and Kumush, precedent statements Siz o'shamu?or begim.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis show that the main sources of a precedent text are mythology and holy books. In Uzbek linguistic culture, Alpomish is honor; Barchin is a place of loyalty; Karabotir - evil, evil enemy; Gorogli - a fearless, brave, brave young man; Layli is a loyal friend; "Majnun" is a national precedent of names taken as a symbol of crazy love. [Muqimova Z, 2022, p.86]. Precedent names can be found not only in the works or stories of this country, but also in the poems of E. Vahidov, A. Aripov, M. Yusuf and etc.

The essential forms of precedent text include the forms that are based on the linguistic mechanism of allusion, such as: phraseological units, proverbs, citations, aphorisms, children's poems, songs and media texts. A precedent situation is an ideal, standard situation that has certain meanings that are popular and known to members of a linguistic and cultural community.

It has been identified that any text of works such as fictions, songs, advertisements, poems or jokes can be the source of precedent texts. Moreover, it can include proverbs, citations, aphorisms, media texts, etc. Togay Murad (Tog'ay Murod)

is one of the writers who used examples of folklore in his works the most. A foreigner who reads his works, even if he has no knowledge of Uzbek ethnography and folklore, will have a lot of knowledge about this culture. A writer can easily convey his culture to his readers with some work rich in powerful images. In this respect, Togay Murad's works are of unprecedented importance in the promotion of Uzbek culture. The main theme of the story "Ot kishnagan oqshom" (The Night of the Horse Neighed) is many. The following proverbs are given in order of appearance in the work. Except for the second-level proverb, all of them are used once in the play. "Kambag'alni tuyaning ustida it qopadi" (b.410), "Ko'rpangga qarab oyoq uzat" (b.414).

CONCLUSION

In general, precedent phenomenon as a unit of discourse represents the cultural and mental values of the nation and linguistic identity, serves as a means of education, actualization of a new meaning and strengthening its expressiveness in a literary text.

In addition, the use of the precedent phenomenon in literature proves the influence of the national picture of the world on the cognition of people of different cultures through a precedent name, situation and precedent statements. Thus, literal precedent phenomena can serve to emphasize significant characteristics through associations in different sources. At the same time, these associations help to clarify the internal mechanism of a literary text and reveal to the reader the hidden meaning of a certain situation.

REFERENCES

1. Zolotarev M. Precedent Phenomena: The role of Cultural Reference in Dostoevsky's novel Demons// thesis. 2013. 2-80.
2. Ismailova M. The features of precedent phenomenon and its types in a literary text// Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal. 2021.
3. Muqimova Z. About the term onomastic metaphor// Nukus. 2022. 86.
4. Darvishov Ibrahim. Text of lectures on linguistic and cultural studies//Namangan. 2021. 56.

5. Захаренко И.В., Красных В.В., Гудков Д.Б., Багаева Д.В. Прецедентное имя и прецедентное высказывание как символы прецедентных феноменов// см. наст. сборник.
6. Караулов, Ю.Н. Русский язык и языковая личность// Москва: ЛКИ, 1987.
7. Караулов Ю.Н. Русский язык и языковая личность// Москва: ЛКИ. 2010.
8. Гудков Д. Б. Прецедентная ситуация и способы ее актуализации. Язык, сознание, коммуникация// Москва: диалог-МГУ. 2000. 40-46.
9. Чуприна О.Г., Баранова К.М., Меркулова М.Г. Судьба как понятие в языке и культуре//2018. 3 (56). 120-125.
10. Tog'ay Murod. Ot kishnagan oqshom//Toshkent. "Sharq" nashriyot-matbaa konsernining Bosh tahririyati. 1994. 178.